

Alternative Explanation for Dark Matter - 8T

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Abstract:

By analyzing the main equation of the new 8T, alongside the equivalence of mass and energy it is possible to present the issue of dark matter in a new way. that is different than the original explanation of dark matter presented in the 8T thesis, which attributed the phenomena to the Quark masses series, predicting a fourth family below first generation. The following paper assumes that this idea is not correct and offer an alternative to it.

Introduction

The 8T setting is a Lorentz manifold, $s = (M, g)$, with (3,1) signature. The manifold is the connected manifold, invoked stationary, $s = s_0 \times \mathbb{R}$. The manifold has areas of extremum curvatures that remain as they are overtime, this are yielding time invariant acceleration from them on the matrix tensor M, given by two conditions below (1). The reason for the acceleration in the 8T is that the manifold is a part of an infinite packet of universes, which interact at areas of extremum curvatures, as g is the Ricci flow, and as a result flatten each other matrix tensor causing it to accelerate in a time invariant rate, given by equations (1.2) and (1.21). By (1.2) those manifolds are topologically invariant.

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0 \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{\partial g}{\partial t} = 0 \cap \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0$$

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s_1} - \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s_n} = 0 \quad (1.1)$$

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s_1} \frac{\partial s_1}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s_n} \frac{\partial s_n}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} = 0 \quad (1.2)$$

The manifold experience arbitrary amount of net curvature isomorphic to prime numbers or the number one. That construction yielded the primorial coupling constants series presented in equations (1.4) to (1.43) present the first and second representation. I.e. net curvature on the matric tensor and the prime critical line.

$$F_{V=0} = 8 + (1) \tag{1.4}$$

$$F_R\# = \left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_V + (3) \right) + N_V = 30:128:850:9254.. \tag{1.41}$$

$$N_V = 2 \left(V + \frac{1}{2} \right); V \geq 0 \tag{1.42}$$

$$N_V \in \mathbb{P} \cup (+1); \mathbb{P} \rightarrow \text{Set of Primes}$$

$$N_V = P_{max} \in [0, \mathbb{R}] \cup (+1); P_{max} \in \mathbb{P}$$

$$8 + (1):(24 + (3)) + 3:(120 + (3)) + 5:(840 + (3)) + 7... \tag{1.43}$$

$$8 + (1)$$

$$[(8 * 3) + (3)] + 3 \rightarrow \left[2N_1 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow \left[2N_2 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$[(120 * 7) + (3)] + 7 \rightarrow \left[2N_3 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

For example, the Electromagnetic coupling term, we have proven the invariant three to be an electron:

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow [(24 * 5) + (e)] + \gamma \quad (1.44)$$

We presented recently the EMT symmetry by the terms (1.45) and (1.46):

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow [(24 * 5) + (\mu^-)] + \gamma \quad (1.45)$$

In addition, the Tau:

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow [(24 * 5) + (\tau^-)] + \gamma \quad (1.46)$$

Up until now, reader is probably familiar with every equation presented, as those are 8T fundamentals. From here on out, we have a completely new paper. In the 8T thesis, we presented the Quark masses series, and predicted an infinite series of families with total mass aspiring zero. Mass is considered arbitrary amount of curvature converging inward, with a symmetry break of the $8 - (1)$ variations. That is the inverse to the primordial, associated with curvature diverging, or $8 + (1)$ variations. In the case of mass generation, nature is devising in increasing amounts to eliminate the arbitrary amounts of curvature. We predicted the total mass of the fourth to be 0.113 Mev, 55-56 times lighter than first. The advantage of this idea is that we no longer need to explain why there are three families.

$$19,600 \rightarrow 1400 \rightarrow 56 \rightarrow 0.113 \dots$$

$$19,600 * 9 \rightarrow 1400 \rightarrow \frac{56}{9} =$$

$$176,400 \rightarrow 1400 \rightarrow 6.3$$

The two versions are presented in the thesis as it is unknown whether the factor of nine is repeating itself for the fifth family and below.

$$M_{N+1} = \frac{M_N + (7)}{7 * \prod_{E=1}^r N_E} * \frac{1}{9} \quad (2)$$

$$M_{N+1} = \frac{M_N + (7)}{7 * \prod_{E=1}^r N_E} \quad (2.1)$$

$$N_E = 2E ; E \geq 1$$

Keeping that in mind, assuming this idea is wrong, what alternative explanation can we offer for the issue of dark matter? Notice that according to the main equation (1) or (1.2) we have an infinite packet of universe which interact at areas of extremum curvatures, that means that there two distinct manifolds (if we regard each manifold to be somewhat of a thin liar), whose extremum curvature interact with our own. Since we are familiar with the equivalence principle between mass and energy, the dark energy as given by equation, can be regarded as dark mass.

Those masses of distinct manifolds may have an additional gravitational interaction. If each manifold has distinct subspaces, which are newer manifolds that rose from the original manifold, those subspaces may interact with the original manifold that means a distinct set of mass, interacting with our own. The advantage of this idea is that, there could not be any additional trait of matter if the matter is own distinct (yet very close to our own) manifold. It seems to be suitable to the fact that dark matter do not do anything other than to exert gravity. The weakness of the original idea is that if there is a fourth family below first, it could behave like original matter, omit and absorb light, which is not in agreement with what we speculate. However, if it is matter on a distinct space, or a infinite spaces of the packet, than the features of dark matter could be explained easier. Summing up, the alternative explanation of dark matter is gravitational effect from a distinct manifold, which interact at areas of extremum curvature. There is advantage to taking the point of view, as it could agree with the features of dark matter behavior. However, using that viewpoint, we still need to explain why there are only three fermions generations. The explanation is not part of this new idea, which is the disadvantage comparing to the original idea. The gravitational effect of dark matter should not be strong, as we have immense fermion clusters, according to the primordial, the ratio of net to total should be very small, aspiring zero, so if dark matter would be explained that route, the gravitational magnitude effect it should have should be weak, that is compared to the first elements in the primordial.

$$\frac{N_V}{T_V} \rightarrow R \tag{2.2}$$

$$0.111 > 0.1 > 0.039 > 0.008 \dots \rightarrow 0$$

We can take the original illustration and modify it

References

- [1] O. Manor. "8 Theory – The Theory of Everything" In: (2021)